

METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH VOCABULARY IN PRIMARY SCHOOL WITH THE HELP OF MODERN PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract: the article deals with using modern pedagogical and technological methods, and by the way introducing leading styles of teaching, teach growing generations, the system of speaking easily in these languages can be developed fully. As well as opportunities in foreign partnership helps to develop it.

Keywords: method, traditional teaching, vocabulary, learning, student, teacher, language, methodology, opportunity.

Nowadays many books and articles are written to attract attention to this point. In planning curricular and methods it has been suggested that an understanding of students and their needs, interest, abilities, likes, dislikes, and developmental status should take precedence over other considerations.

By using modern pedagogical and technological methods, and by the way introducing leading styles of teaching, teach growing generations, the system of speaking easily in these languages can be developed fully. As well as opportunities in foreign partnership helps to develop it. Known to us, using innovations and new pedagogical technologies are resulting well. Sometimes using same styles in teaching language may let go down interests of student to language. We advise some types of teaching in use, not to go down interest to foreign language. The growing interest in many parts of the world in Modern Methods of Teaching English brings with it the question of how it should be done – how curriculum, subject, matter, and methodology should differ from the familiar norms developed

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in the past. A lot has been written on traditional teaching English, and until recently, the demand for the information on modern methods of teaching English has been limited. For instance: Dialogical speech – in this way students have a talk each other by creative approach.

“Modern methodology of teaching English puts speaking in Dialogues in the first place for developing speaking skills. These skills can be trained with various teaching aids, including texts of fiction. Such dialogues give an opportunity to avoid traditional rendering of the texts and turn them into living English speech”. More than that, all the vocabulary is remembered much better.

In dialogues, students train in fluency, quick reaction, acting skills and, of course, grammatical correctness. Student reads the text himself and tells the meaning. Reading is interactive. Reading short stories, novels and other literary works written by famous Uzbek, English and American writers is very important in language learning. As a teacher of English you may apply a variety of reading strategies, analyze literary elements use a variety of strategies to read unfamiliar words and build vocabulary, prepare, organize, and present literary interpretations. Understanding by listening – by these way students can improve speech skills. Listening is a receptive form of speech activity.

Comprehension of speech while listening mainly based on auditory feelings. By perceiving, reproduce what we hear, in the form of inwardly speech. Listening comprehension is impossible without working of speech motor analyzer. Of course internal speaking requires ability to speak in this language. Understanding of sounding speech, in the moment of comprehension, is accompanied by intellectual activity, which includes recognizing of speech means and interpretation of the content. Nowadays, teachers take into consideration students’ demands for watching real movie stories together with reading books, magazines and newspapers. Because, as it is known not only printed materials can serve as a great source of teaching but also songs and movies play a key role in learning foreign

languages. Vocabulary is one of the aspects of the language to be taught in the institutes. In addition to learn new vocabulary, learner need to able to use strategies to cope with unknown vocabulary met in listening or reading text, to make up for gaps in productive vocabulary in speaking and writing to gain fluency in using known vocabulary and to learn new words in isolation. Vocabulary learning is not on end in itself.

A rich vocabulary makes to perform the skills of listening, speaking, reading and writing easier. By the type of teaching in traditional style is divided into several aspects such as speaking, analytic reading, reading at home, practice grammar, practical phonetics. As a result 3-4 teachers teach students in variety styles and as a result the connection of aspects is not provided [1, c. 87]. For instance, at the beginning of lesson teacher makes plan and shares news with students. Each student participates in this plan and shares news with each others. As a result mutual exchanging of knowledge is appeared and all students get to know the theme. Some exercises are done by couple or group of students. For working in the group students are given such tasks: organize debates, debate the theme with playing roles, and work with high techs. To work in couple they are given dialogues, grammar materials, and also reading. Some students learn grammar well, but in speech they meet difficulties to pronounce words [2, c. 236]. Moreover there are some methods to improve learning foreign language. Lessons are fully taught in English language based on all experiences, which are needed for lessons. That is to say students begin to understand by reading, by listening, practice of writing, improve speech and others. Students are become focal point of lessons, not teachers. The teacher only helps student to get knowledge. In this way the possibility of self studying is got well. When lessons aren't traditional, tasks are divided into couple or small group of students due to the type of it, students work in groups or individually.

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